

MANAGEMENT OF RECURRENT EAR KELOID WITH VIBHITAKI KSHARA SUTRA – AN AYURVEDIC CASE REPORT

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ABSTRACT

Background: Keloids are benign fibroproliferative disorders caused by excessive collagen deposition during wound healing. Auricular keloids are cosmetically distressing and are associated with high recurrence rates despite conventional treatments such as intralesional steroid injections and surgical excision. In Ayurveda, keloids can be correlated with Vrana Granthi for which Kshara Sutra therapy is indicated. **Case Presentation:** A 25-year-old female presented with a recurrent keloid over the left ear lobule, persisting for two years following ear piercing. She had previously undergone injection therapy and surgical excision, after which recurrence occurred. Vibhitaki Kshara Sutra ligation was performed under aseptic conditions. **Results:** The keloid mass underwent gradual necrosis and sloughed off completely within 14 days. Complete wound healing was observed in 2 months. No complications or recurrence were noted during follow-up. **Conclusion:** Vibhitaki Kshara Sutra ligation is a safe, minimally invasive, cost-effective, and efficient Ayurvedic modality for the management of recurrent auricular keloids with satisfactory cosmetic outcomes and minimal recurrence risk.

KEYWORDS: Keloid, Kshara Sutra, Vrana Granthi.

INTRODUCTION

Keloids are abnormal fibroproliferative growths that extend beyond the original wound margins due to excessive collagen deposition during wound healing. Auricular keloids commonly occur following ear piercing and are more prevalent in young females. Despite various treatment modalities including surgical excision, intralesional corticosteroids, pressure therapy, radiotherapy, and LASER, recurrence rates remain high, ranging from 50–80%.^[1]

In Ayurvedic literature, keloids can be correlated with Vrana Granthi of Karnapali, classified under Mamsadhatu Pradoshaja Vyadhi. Classical texts describe Kshara Karma and Kshara Sutra as effective parasurgical measures for abnormal tissue growths, offering controlled chemical cauterization and minimal recurrence.^[2,3] This case report aims to evaluate the

efficacy of Vibhitaki Kshara Sutra in the management of recurrent auricular keloid.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Study Design

Single case interventional study.

Patient Information

A 25-year-old female presented with a gradually progressive swelling over the left ear lobule for two years. The lesion developed following ear piercing. She had a history of injection therapy and surgical excision two years earlier, followed by recurrence.

Clinical Findings

- Site: Left ear lobule
- Size: 4 × 3 cm
- Shape: Lobulated, irregular

- Consistency: Firm
- Tenderness: Absent
- Fixity: Absent

No systemic illness or significant family history was present.

Treatment

Purva Karma

1. Patient Evaluation
 - History, clinical examination
 - Evaluate for infection and comorbidities
2. Consent
 - Procedure details and risks explained; informed consent obtained.
3. Local Preparation
 - Site cleaned with Betadine solution and spirit.
 - Vibhitaki Kshara Sutra loaded on artery forceps

Pradhana Karma

- Under aseptic precautions, part preparation and draping done.
- Injection LOX 2% was infiltrated around the base of the keloid.

- Vibhitaki Kshara Sutra was tightly ligated at the base of the keloid.

Paschat Karma

- The patient was monitored for pain, inflammation, discoloration, and necrosis.
- Dressing with Jatyadi Taila was done once every three days for two weeks.

Oral Medication

- Cap Grab 1-0-1 for 30 days
- Tablet Taxim-O 200 mg BD for 5 days
- Tablet Zerodol-P BD
- Tablet Pan 40 mg OD

RESULTS

Gradual ischemic necrosis of the keloid tissue was observed following Kshara Sutra ligation. Complete sloughing of the keloid occurred within 14 days. The wound healed completely within 40 days with healthy granulation tissue formation. No infection, excessive scarring, or recurrence was observed during the follow-up period.

DISCUSSION

Kshara Sutra therapy acts through controlled chemical cauterization, causing strangulation of blood supply to pathological tissue and inducing gradual necrosis. Vibhitaki (*Terminalia bellirica*) possesses Kashaya Rasa,

Ruksha Guna, Madhura Vipaka, Krimighna and Shothahara properties, which contribute to tissue contraction, slough removal, infection prevention, and wound healing.^[4,5] Unlike surgical excision, which may stimulate fibroblast proliferation and recurrence, Kshara

Sutra allows precise tissue destruction with minimal damage to surrounding structures. Studies published in integrative journals have demonstrated the effectiveness of Kshara Sutra in managing chronic proliferative conditions with reduced recurrence rates.^[6,7]

CONCLUSION

Vibhitaki Kshara Sutra ligation is an effective, minimally invasive Ayurvedic parasurgical technique for the management of recurrent auricular keloids. It provides satisfactory cosmetic outcomes, minimal complications, and low recurrence rates. This modality may be considered a promising alternative to conventional surgical methods. Further clinical studies with larger sample sizes are required for validation.

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